

Impulse versus Pressure or Quantum Versus Classical in Reflection / Refraction

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In classical statistical mechanics, e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas, one calculates pressure by multiplying $2p$ (impulse) by v (velocity or flux). This is done because one has multiple particles and so flux is important. One needs to know how many particles strike a surface per sec as well as their impulse. What happens if one has a single photon (or particle)? This is not a steady stream situation, although one may create a corresponding steady stream situation. In particular, a single photon moving in the positive x direction may reach an interface of two media with different indices of refraction and either reflect or refract. In such a case one has a probability to reflect and one to refract which add to 1. Thus there are two unknowns (i.e. the two probabilities) and energy stays constant.

One may immediately write a conservation of energy equation and apply it to a steady state scenario. This necessarily utilizes the idea of velocity because there is a flux. This energy conservation equation may be rearranged to give the appearance of a pressure balance equation which also depends on velocity i.e. flux. The problem is that conservation of energy or pressure balance is a single equation and there are two unknowns. One may not simply say that the probability to reflect is .5 and that to refract .5.

In fact, in a previous note (1) we solved this problem using the idea of writing the energy equation in terms of two equations linked to differences of squares. We suggested that these two equations which only involve weights are linked to a function which together with its first derivative is continuous at $x=0$. In (2) we suggested that the x -distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent action-reaction impulse type distributions. We argued that an impulse creates momentum p in the first place and that this "impulse", in the form of x -distributions, is still present because the object may strike a foil and impart impulse at any time. Furthermore, because $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are probability distributions, there is no sense of time within a wavelength. On average, however, the object moves with a constant velocity. In the case of light it is c/n where n is the index of refraction and in the case of a nonrelativistic particle p/m_0 .

The example of a single photon either reflecting or refracting allows one to formulate the problem in terms of impulse i.e. in terms of the probability distribution scheme such that one does not have time and hence velocity. This scheme requires two equations. This impulse based x -probability distribution scheme or quantum mechanical approach, however, should map into the classical pressure balance because on average a photon does move as $x=c/n t$ which it does. It is, however, the quantum approach (impulse picture with no time or velocity within a wavelength) which solves the problem i.e. yields the probability to reflect or refract which may then be linked to classical type (steady stream intensities and flux).

Reflection/Refraction Conservation of Energy Equation

Consider a photon moving in the positive x direction reaching the interface of two media at $x=0$ with indices of refraction of $n=1$ and n_2 with $n_2 > n$. The photon may reflect or refract, but its energy remains E which is its initial energy. Thus it seems unnecessary to write a conservation

of energy equation. Such an equation, however, makes sense in the case of a steady state flux picture with many photons. Incident energy flux is then given as:

$$AA = E n(A) c \quad \text{where } n(A) \text{ is the number of incident photons } ((1))$$

Similarly there is BB and CC for the reflected and refracted situations. Ultimately there is an overall energy conservation equation which utilizes speed or flux:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c \quad ((2))$$

If AA is given, there exist two unknowns B and C, but ((2)) is a single equation and so there is a problem. Let us ignore this for the time being and rewrite ((2)) in terms of pressure. Classically pressure is based on impulse proportional to p multiplied by v i.e. velocity of flux.

For a photon: $E = |p|c$ so ((2)) is equivalent to:

$$AA p - p BB = CC p^2 \quad \text{where } p^2 = p n^2 > p \quad ((3))$$

((1)) shows that AA, BB CC contain speed so ((3)) contains p multiplied by speed and so represents a kind of pressure balance. Again there is only one equation and one cannot solve for B and C in terms of A.

To sum up, steady state energy conservation or pressure balance makes use of the notion of speed which implies infinite resolution of x space and is deterministic. The problem is that these classical notions do not allow one to solve the problem i.e. find B,C in terms of A.

To find B, C one has to drop the classical picture and replace it with a quantum one which pertains to a single photon and is based on the notion of impulse described in terms of an x-probability distribution so time disappears within a wavelength and there is no velocity. This quantum approach, however, may be mapped into the classical approach which does not make use of a built-in x probability distribution to describe action-reaction, but uses speeds i.e. fluxes.

Reflection-Refraction and a Single Photon

The traditional way to solve the reflection/refraction is given in (3) and uses the notion of continuity of the electric field and its first x derivative at $x=0$. Maxwell found from his electromagnetic equations that he could describe a photon with an electric field varying as $\cos(\omega t - px)$ ($\hbar = 1$). To simplify mathematically, $\exp(ipx)$ may be used instead because one has linear terms and $\exp(-iEt)$ may be dropped because E is the same for the incident/reflected and refracted photon. (3) then leads to:

$$A+B = C \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad pA - pB = p^2 C \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{at } x=0 \text{ i.e. } \exp(ip_0)=1$$

For $n < n_2$, $B < 0$.

In (1) we argued that one does not need information about the behaviour of the electric field. One may take the conservation of energy equation (written in terms of flux) ((2)) and write it as a difference of squares, keeping p intact. This immediately yields ((4a) and ((4b)).

Let us examine ((4a)) and ((4b)) more closely. If $B < 0$ then $B = -|B|$. This allows ((4a)) to be written as a probability statement for a single photon i.e.

$$A = |B| + C \text{ with } A, |B| \text{ and } C \text{ all } > 0 \text{ and } A > C \quad ((5))$$

If A is set to 1, then $|B|$ and C represent the probabilities to reflect or refract. At this point there is no connection of A, B, C with the intensities A_A, B_B, C_C of ((2)).

((5)) is an automatic statement, but it is a single equation, another is needed to solve for B, C . This second equation is ((4b)), but interestingly this equation does not make use of velocity, only p which represents impulse. Thus one uses a probability together with impulse with no notion of velocity of flux. We argue that this is in keeping with $\exp(ipx)$ with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ representing probability distributions such that one has no notion of time or velocity. Thus one balances impulse times its probability in the distributions $\cos(px), \sin(px)$ at $x=0$ multiplied by the weights of A, B or C . Thus ((4b)) is equivalent to:

$$Ap = |B|(-p) + p^2 C \text{ where } A, |B|, C > 0 \text{ and } p^2 > p \text{ and } p^2, p > 0 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is a quantum mechanical equation (essential for solving the reflection/refraction problem) and its physical foundation is impulse balance with no velocity/flux concept present. ((5)) is an automatically obvious equation. Thus one has two equations and may solve for B and C in terms of A .

We stress that dropping velocity or flux means there must be a picture in which one cannot know velocity i.e. in which there is no longer determinism i.e. $x=ct$. This suggests a probability scenario i.e. an x -distribution. In classical statistical mechanics it may be noted that a spatial distribution is linked with a force through $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ where $V(x)$ is the potential and T temperature. We suggest that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ also indicate an action-reaction type of force present linked to the impulse represented by p . It is this physical picture which allows one to solve the reflection/refraction problem.

Linking Quantum Mechanical Impulse Back to the Classical Scenario

((4a)) and ((4b)) allow one to solve the reflection-refraction problem. We have already noted that ((4a)) and ((4b)) may be obtained from ((2)) (the classical picture with flux) by using differences of squares. Thus the impulse -no time quantum picture maps into the classical one with fluxes. In the classical scenario with fluxes, one no longer has a single photon, but rather a steady stream. In such a case velocity is important as it is linked to flux. Physically a single photon is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ which shows the internal impulse distributions are also linked to $x=ct$. Thus on average (i.e. with many particles) $x=ct$ must emerge again. By multiplying ((4a)) and

((4b)) together one obtains terms AA, BB and CC which are guaranteed to be positive and so candidates for intensity. In such a case, one may then think in terms of velocity as in a classical picture which drops the internal action-reaction x- probability distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have previously examined the reflection/refraction problem in (1). There we used the idea of a conservation of energy equation written in terms of a flux picture being broken into two equations using a difference of squares. We thus suggested that there was a different picture (than the classical flux one) needed to solve for the intensities of reflected and refracted beams in terms of the incident.

In this note we wish to consider the physical concepts associated with the two situations namely the single classical conservation of energy in a flux picture and the quantum two equation situation. The flux picture applies to many photons (just as the classical statistical mechanical picture applies to many particles.) There the concept of pressure is used i.e. impulse p (or $2p$) is multiplied by v linked to flux. In such a case, one may ascertain speeds. In the reflection-refraction steady state case with many photons one may again include speed in the intensity expression $AA = E n(A) c$ because there is a flux of energy. One divides by c to obtain an expression for $En(A)$. The energy conservation equation in terms of flux may also be written as a pressure balance equation as we have shown in the note. This again involves the concept of speed. Unfortunately there is only one equation and two unknowns B,C in terms of A.

A different physical scheme is required to obtain two equations needed to find B,C in terms of A. This scheme involves considering a single photon. In such a case there is an immediate equation namely the conservation of probability given by $A = |B| + C$. A second equation involves the idea of impulse balance (not pressure balance) . This implies that flux or velocity is not in the picture. How can that be? On average a photon must move with speed c . We suggest that an impulse is associated with an x-probability distribution (actually two) in $\exp(ipx)$. Thus within a wavelength $= \hbar/p$ there is a probability to be at x given by $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ for the orthogonal piece. Given probability there cannot be determinism and hence no $x=ct$ i.e. no t and no c . Physically one balances impulses using the probabilities A, |B| and C i.e. $Ap = |B|(-p) + pC$ where $p_2 = pn_2$, n_2 being the index of refraction of the second medium with $n_1=1$. This approach yields the two equations: $A+B+C$ and $pA-pB = p_2C$ which mathematically are of the form of a continuity equation at $x=0$ using $A\exp(ipx)$, $B\exp(-ipx)$ and $C\exp(ip_2x)$ and grouping in space.

Finally we note that the quantum or impulse picture maps into the classical flux type approach because the two quantum equations multiplied together yields an equation which may be interpreted as a conservation of energy written in terms of a flux/speed values.

Thus we argue that quantum mechanics involves solving a problem by using the knowledge of the x-distributions associated with impulse (momentum). The x-distributions are probabilities so one may only use the deterministic $x=vt$ form on average i.e. applying to many particles or to an average situation.

References

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